

THE SIZE OF THE PLASTIC ZONE IN FRONT OF AN ADVANCING DELAMINATION AT AN INTERFACE WITH DISSIMILAR FIBRE ORIENTATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A study has been performed to explain the observed increase in mode I fracture toughness for composite laminates with off-axis fibre orientations at the crack interface. A critical evaluation has been made towards the applicability of linear-elastic fracture mechanics, as used in the DCB- and modified DCB (MDCB) procedures, for non-linear elasto-plastic material systems. A comparison has been made of three different calculation procedures for the strain-energy-release rate at a mode I crack tip in a composite laminate for varying fibre off-axis angles, and therefore varying elasto-plastic properties. Calculation methods used were the linear-elastic G-calculation technique and two techniques based on the non-linear elastic J-integral : the Derbalian-approximation and an actual line-integral calculation. Comparisons have been made using load-displacement curves obtained from finite element analysis for a composite beam structure with varying material properties subjected to mode I loading. Relative differences of up to 20% with respect to the linear-elastic strain-energy-release rate values have been calculated.

Keywords : fracture toughness, plasticity

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of two new test procedures [1] to determine the mode I and mode II critical strain-energy-release rates for composite laminates with varying fibre orientations at the delamination interface, it has become apparent that the non-linear elasto-plastic properties of the matrix play an important role with respect to the observed increase in the mode I fracture toughness, G_{Ic} , for increasing fibre off-axis orientation, Figure 1.

Because of the very high stiffness of the fibre reinforcement with respect to the stiffness of the surrounding matrix, the longitudinal on-axis composite properties for a unidirectional laminate will show negligible non-linear behaviour. Therefore, for this case of unidirectional laminates, matrix non-linear behaviour will have practically no influence upon the fracture toughness results obtained from standard DCB and ELS experiments. Consequently, standard calculation procedures derived

from linear elastic fracture mechanics will be sufficiently accurate to calculate G_{IC} and G_{IIc} values from the observed loads and deformations during DCB and ELS fracture toughness experiments.

When matrix non-linearity becomes more important, like for high off-axis fibre angles, not only the local load and deformation, but also the complete load-displacement history before crack growth will influence the total energy consumed. Part of the consumed energy will contribute to the formation of the plastic zone in front of the advancing crack. To determine the mode I and mode II fracture toughness values for off-axis fibre orientations, the non-linear properties of the composite will have an increasing effect upon the strain-energy-release rate at the crack tip. The G-calculation procedures will no longer be valid and the J-integral technique will have to be used [2].

The following paper describes the theoretical approach followed to evaluate the strain-energy-release rate for mode I testing of non-linear elasto-plastic materials. This evaluation has been applied on carbon/epoxy 3501/AS4 laminates (6376/HTA elasto-plastic properties were not yet available) with equivalent fibre orientations as in the experimental program to determine the fracture toughness of multidirectional interfaces.

Figure 1 : Mode I (M)DCB configuration and fracture toughness values for multidirectional interfaces.

2. THEORETICAL

The strain-energy-release rate at a crack-tip is defined as :

$$G = \frac{dW}{da} - \frac{dU}{da} \quad (1)$$

Here W is the work performed by the applied loading, U the strain-energy density and da an infinitesimal amount of crack growth. For linear elastic behaviour U only consists of its elastic strain energy component U^{el} , while for elastic-plastic response it is convenient to separate U in its elastic and plastic parts.

$$U = \int \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij}^{el} + \int_0^{\varepsilon_{ij}^{pl}} \sigma_{ij} d\varepsilon_{ij}^{pl} = U^{el} + U^{pl} \quad (2)$$

To evaluate the delamination resistance of composite materials the strain-energy-release rate at a crack tip at the moment the crack starts to grow is determined. This value is called the critical

strain-energy-release rate or fracture toughness of the material and laminate under consideration and for a given load situation. To determine the fracture toughness for an opening mode I loading, the most accepted method for the calculation of G_{Ic} is the 'Double Cantilever Beam'-method, Figure 1.

2.1. Linear elastic material behaviour

In this case the strain energy only consists of its elastic part and the strain-energy-release rate can be described by G . The elastic strain energy for the mode I load case can easily be calculated from the applied load by using standard beam theory. Assuming constant opening displacements (assuming a fixed load would eventually give the same result), no work will be performed by the external loads and the energy release is calculated as the change in strain energy when the crack is advanced an infinitesimal amount da . This energy amounts to the area enclosed by triangle ABC in Figure 2a. The fracture toughness being the energy needed per unit area of crack growth, the mode I fracture toughness G_{Ic} can directly be calculated from the observed load (P) and opening displacement (δ) at crack growth during DCB testing with :

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{2 \cdot P \cdot \delta}{3 \cdot B \cdot a} \tag{3}$$

2.2. Non-linear material behaviour

When non-linear elasto-plastic material behaviour is considered, a small zone at the crack tip will deform plastically due to the stress concentration. Within a plastically deformed structure, part of the energy will be consumed by this plastic deformation which can not be recovered. Consequently, for identical loads and displacements, less elastic energy will be present in the structure, area BCD with respect to area ABC in Figure 2b, so less energy can be released at crack growth when compared to the linear-elastic case, the light shaded area in Figure 2c. Apparent fracture toughness values, G_C 's, based on the linear-elastic calculation, will therefore tend to overestimate the real fracture toughness of the material.

Figure 2 : Energy consumed during crack growth for the mode I load case.

2.2.1. The Derbalian Calculation

As first method to calculate the energy released at crack growth, an approximate calculation technique can be used that calculates the difference in total energy contained in the structure for two different crack lengths. Within this procedure, the ratio of the loads for both crack lengths a and

$a+da$ is taken constant for all opening displacements, even in the plastic range. This approximation has been derived by Derbalian [3].

$$\frac{P(a+da)}{P(a)} = Ct \quad \text{for all opening displacements} \quad (4)$$

Introducing this approximation into (2), the strain energy release is calculated as the dark shaded area in Figure 2c. Because $P(a)$ and $P(a+da)$ will be equal for both the Derbalian and the linear-elastic DCB calculation (because both values are calculated using the same standard linear-elastic beam bending equations for both the DCB and the Derbalian calculations), the energy-release rate calculated with the Derbalian approximation will always be greater or equal to the DCB value as can directly be seen from the figure.

The strain-energy-release rate, being the energy released per unit area of crack growth, can then be calculated with :

$$G \cong - \frac{1}{B.P} \frac{dP}{da} \int P.d\delta \quad (5)$$

Here B is the width of the specimen. The factor dP/da , like proposed by Derbalian, is assumed constant over the elastic and plastic region of the load-displacement curve. Consequently, this factor can be calculated from two linear-elastic FEM analyses for two different crack lengths, or it can be calculated from linear-elastic beam theory. The latter was chosen in the present work. In total, the relation becomes :

$$\frac{1}{B.P} \frac{dP}{da} = \frac{1}{B} \frac{3.\delta.EI}{2.a^3} \frac{d}{da} \left(\frac{3.\delta.EI}{2.a^3} \right) = \frac{3}{B.a} \quad (6)$$

The external work performed during the load cycle is obtained from the registered or calculated load-displacement during experiments or FEM simulation respectively.

2.2.2. The J-integral

Another method to calculate the strain-energy-release rate for non-linear elastic materials, which can be applied to elasto-plastic materials as well through the use of the deformation theory of plasticity (as long as no unloading occurs), is the so called J-integral technique. This technique was introduced by Rice [4]. In its simplest two-dimensional form, J is defined as a path-independent line integral, based upon an energy conservation theorem, that measures the intensity of the singular stresses and strains near a crack tip. Rice has shown that the J-integral as defined along a contour around the crack tip is the change in potential energy V for a virtual crack extension da :

$$J = - \frac{\partial V}{\partial a} = \int_{\Gamma} U dy - \int_{\Gamma} t_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} ds \quad (7)$$

Here Γ is any path surrounding the crack tip, U the strain energy density, t_i the traction vector, u_i the displacement vector, x the coordinate direction parallel to the plane of the crack, s the distance along the path Γ and V the potential energy. The finite element package ANSYS is supplied with an appropriate routine to calculate the integrals as specified in (7).

3. EXPERIMENTAL

Within this research project the mentioned G_{IC} calculation procedures have been evaluated and compared for various non-linear elasto-plastic material systems. A DCB structure as in Figure 1 has been loaded with increasing loads (this structure is equivalent to the MDCB configuration which only differs from the DCB method in the specimen lamination procedure).

For each load value, see Table 1, the non-linear elasto-plastic opening displacement has been calculated using the ANSYS 4.4 FEM software package.

For each of these load-displacement combinations, the strain-energy-release rate, G_I , has been calculated with the standard DCB procedure (equal to the Modified DCB procedure) which assumes linear-elastic behaviour up to each load-displacement point, and with the two non-linear elasto-plastic methods incorporating the total load-displacement history foregoing each load-point.

To compare calculated and experimental values, the load-displacement point calculated from FEM analysis at which the linear-elastic calculated strain-energy-release rate G_{IC} equals the experimental MDCB toughness G_{IC} is taken as the point for comparison.

$$P \rightarrow \delta_{FEM} \rightarrow G_{DCB} = \frac{3 \cdot P \cdot \delta_{FEM}}{2 \cdot B \cdot a} \quad \& \quad G_{Derbalan} \quad \& \quad J_{FEM}$$

$$G_{DCB} = G_{IC_{MDCB}} ? \xrightarrow{YES} G_{IC_{Derbalan}} \quad \& \quad J_{IC_{FEM}}$$

Table 1 : Evaluation Procedure Scheme.

3.1. The finite element mesh

Two-dimensional finite element calculations have been made for the DCB load configuration as in Figure 1. Crack length, a , has been taken 50mm and half specimen thickness $h = 5$ mm (out of meshing considerations). Because of symmetry only one half of the beam was modelled. The mesh has been built up of 6-noded triangular elements which have been concentrated around the crack-tip. For the case of linear-elastic material behaviour, which was present for the 0° case of the carbon-epoxy laminate, singular crack-tip elements have been used ($r^{-1/2}$ singularity). For plastic behaviour standard 6-noded triangular elements (r^{-1} singularity for perfectly plastic behaviour) have been used. Calculations have been performed assuming plane strain conditions.

3.2. Materials

The material to be evaluated was the same carbon-epoxy material used in the Modified DCB (MDCB) fracture toughness experiments. For this material, the 3501/AS4 carbon-epoxy, three cases have been evaluated, each for a different fibre off-axis orientation. Fibre off-axis angles have been taken to be 0° , 15° and 30° to be able to compare calculated values with experimental data.

Within the first stage of this research project, material properties of the carbon-epoxy have been assumed isotropic (leading to an overestimation of the out-of-plane yield stress, and consequently a conservative approach to the calculation of plastic energy), while the materials non-linear properties for each off-axis angle have been calculated using the one parameter model by Sun and Chen [5] This model defines a single flow parameter for each material system to be determined from tensile tests for one or more specific fibre off-axis angles. Stress-strain relationships for every other off-axis angle can then be calculated using the same value for this flow parameter.

Stress-strain relations for the used off-axis angles are plotted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 : Non-linear stress-strain curves for various off-axis angles. calculated according to the Sun & Chen model [4].

3.3. Results

Results of the finite element calculations are presented in Figures 4 and 5 for the 0° and 30° case. The calculated values for the strain-energy-release rate at the reference points have been compared with the fracture toughness data determined from MDCB experiments, Table 2.

Off-axis angle (°)	MDCB	Derbalian	Relative to MDCB	J-integral	Relative to MDCB
00°	196	188	-4%	176	-10%
15°	215	207	-4%	184	-14%
30°	266	275	+4%	217	-19%

Table 2 : Experimental and theoretical fracture toughness values.

Figure 4 : Strain-energy-release rates for an off-axis angle off 00°

Figure 5 : Strain-energy-release rate values for an off-axis angle of 30°.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Comparison of calculation techniques

As can be seen from Figure 4, the energy-release rates calculated with the Derbalian method are almost equal to the linear elastic DCB values for linear-elastic material behaviour (the 0° case - differences are probably due to the approximative nature of the FEM method itself). This is according to what could be expected because in both cases the area enclosed by the load and unload cycle is equal to the triangle as in Figure 2.

For non-linear elasto-plastic materials however, Figure 5, the Derbalian method obtains higher values because in this case the total energy difference is calculated, and consequently part of the plastic energy is incorporated in these calculations. As plastic behaviour becomes more pronounced like for increasing fibre off-axis angles, the difference between the DCB values and the Derbalian calculations increases.

The J-integral on the other hand seems to underestimate the strain-energy-release rate because for linear elastic material behaviour, every method used should turn out to give the same value. However, while the DCB and Derbalian method (to calculate dP/da) use only bending deformations, no shear deformations are incorporated. Accordingly, this will lead to an overestimation of the bending stiffness and strain-energy-release rates. The J-integral on the other hand, giving lower values, takes this shear deformation into account.

4.2. Fracture toughness values

From Table 2 it can directly be seen that indeed the fracture toughness G_{TC} will be overestimated when material non-linearity is not accounted for. Although this effect will not be present for on-axis fibre orientation, like in standard 0° DCB and ELS tests, this effect can increase severely for increasing off-axis angles.

Even though some severe simplifications were introduced to perform the finite element calculations : isotropic and homogeneous material behaviour, it is believed that introducing non-isotropic properties will even increase the reported discrepancies. This can be explained by the fact that the stiffness and strength in the transverse and out-of-plane directions will be lower than for the assumed isotropic material (in this case the stiffness and strength is equal for all directions). Therefore yield

stresses in these directions will be attained faster, which will cause more plastic energy to be consumed.

The effect of the fibres on the development of the matrix plastic zone is still unclear for the moment, though this aspect is currently being investigated in a collaborative project with the Université Catholique de Louvain [6].

Because the evaluated carbon-epoxy 3501/AS4 is of a rather brittle nature, the relative importance of the plastic energy will probably become higher for tougher materials like the 6376/HTA, or even thermoplastic material systems.

5. CONCLUSION

From finite element calculations it was found that for standard unidirectional on-axis DCB experiments, the available calculation methods to obtain the mode I fracture toughness G_{IC} are sufficiently accurate.

For materials or off-axis directions showing considerable non-linear elasto-plastic behaviour, standard linear-elastic relations no longer describe the real energy consuming mechanisms. Relative fracture toughness overestimations of about 20% have been reported even for the brittle 3501/AS4 carbon-epoxy.

Although the calculations have been carried out with the introduction of some major approximations, it was made plausible that these approximations would tend to underestimate the above plastic effect. A more elaborate study on these effects will be reported in the near future.

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7. REFERENCES

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